

Deliverable D10.11.

Data Management Plan (DMP)

Deliverable report

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (WP7 - Mechanisms for social awareness & interaction with policymakers) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analysed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allow a close follow-up of main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them along the whole project activities. Among potential social risks, impact in the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AI	Artificial intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Management
CA	Consortium Agreement
CAN	Controller Area Network
CFS	Certificate on the Financial Statements
CSV	Comma-separated values, open text format
DEQ	DIGIECOQUARRY
DGPS	Differential Global Positioning System
DMP	Data management plan
DoA	Description of Action
DPIA	Data protection impact assessments
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DWH	Data warehouse
DXF	Drawing Interchange Format, or Drawing Exchange Format
EB	Exploitation Board
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H&S	Health and Safety
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
IoT	Internet Of Things
IP (R)	Intellectual property (Rights)
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying System
IWMS	Integrated Workplace Management System
JPEG	Joint Photographic Experts Group, recording format for a compressed digital representation of a still image
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation, lightweight format for storing and transporting data
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KTA	Key Technology Area

Abbreviation	Description
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PDF	Portable document format, text file format
POPD	Protection of Personal Data
SQL	Structured Query Language used by databases
SW	Software
TXT	file extension for a Text file
WLAN	Wireless Local Area Network
WP	Work Package
XML	eXtensible Markup Language
ZIP	file compression format

1 Executive Summary

This document constitutes the second and final version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the DIGIECOQUARRY project. It serves as a comprehensive guide for the management of data generated throughout the project, ensuring alignment with key principles of digitalization, data governance, and compliance with European standards and regulations.

The report provides an overview of the key components involved in the digitalization process within DIGIECOQUARRY, offering detailed descriptions of the selected components and their roles in achieving the project's objectives. It also outlines the principles and guidelines necessary to address critical issues such as FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) data principles, Open Access requirements, and GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) compliance. These guidelines establish the foundation for effective data governance and facilitate seamless data sharing within and beyond the project.

Moreover, a comprehensive list of datasets generated during the testing and validation phases at pilot sites is presented in Annex 1. These datasets, created under near-real-world conditions, embody the project's commitment to supporting the digital transformation of quarry processes. The datasets are designed with adaptability and interoperability in mind, featuring generic data models for transport, production, and environmental impact analysis.

By adhering to the FAIR principles, these models ensure that the data produced can be accessed, shared, and reused effectively, contributing to the sustainability and scalability of digitalization efforts in quarrying operations. This DMP reflects the DIGIECOQUARRY project's dedication to fostering innovation, collaboration, and transparency, providing a valuable resource for future initiatives in similar domains.

This final version of the DMP encapsulates the project's strategic approach to data management and its enduring impact on the digitalization of quarry processes, setting a benchmark for efficient and responsible data handling.

This deliverable corresponds to Task 10.4 of Work Package (WP) 10 'Data Management Plan (DMP) and Gender Action Plan and monitoring'.

2 Introduction

2.1 Objectives of the project

DIGIECOQUARRY is a Horizon 2020 project aiming to design, develop and validate in 5 pilot environments an Innovative Quarrying System (IQS) comprising sensors, processes, tools and methods for data capture, processing and sharing to provide integrated, digitalised, automatic and real-time process control for aggregates quarries (Figure 1).

The DIGIECOQUARRY consortium combined the latest researched and advanced technologies applied to quarry operation together with the integration of selected innovative digital solutions to boost the capacity of the aggregates industry, to enhance Health & Safety conditions for workers, to improve the Process and Efficiency of the aggregates extractive sites, to maximise Sustainability and Resource Efficiency in the quarry operations and to foster Social Acceptance.

Figure 1. DIGIECOQUARRY concept.

2.2 Purpose of the document

This deliverable materializes the final version of the Data Management Plan elaborated by DIGIECOQUARRY. The purpose of this document is to provide an overview of the dataset types present in the project, to collect the main data management policy adopted by the Consortium and identify the list of data to be shared by the project.

The data management plan defines how data in general and research data in particular were handled during the research project and will make suggestions for the after-project time. It describes what data was collected, processed or generated, which methodologies and standards were followed during the collection process, whether and how these data were shared and/or made open in the context of “Open access to scientific publications and underlying research data” defined by article 29.2.

This deliverable has been updated in line with the progress of the project. It represents the second and final planned version:

- The initial version (D10.4) was delivered in Month 6 (November 2021).
- This document corresponds to the final version (D10.11), delivered in Month 47 (April 2025).

2.3 Intended audience

The dissemination level of D10.4 is ‘public’ (PU) and available to members of the consortium, the Commission (EC) services and those external to the project.

This document is primarily intended to serve as an internal guideline and reference for all DIGIECOQUARRY beneficiaries, especially the governance bodies such as the General Assembly, the Project Management Board, the Project Technical Committee, and the International Advisory Board.

3 Data in DIGIECOQUARRY: An Overview

3.1 Data management methodology in DIGIECOQUARRY

Data Management Plan (DMP) is a brief plan to define what data sets the project generated or processed, whether and how these data were made accessible, and how they were curated, stored and preserved. The DMP should also provide information on the measures taken to safeguard and protect sensitive data. Some personal information - such as a person's origin, political opinion, religious beliefs, health, trade union membership, or sexual orientation - is classified as sensitive personal data.

This document will help beneficiaries make their research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) as described in section 6.

The data generated had different formats [e.g., Excel Tables, JPEG, CSV, DXF, JSON, etc.] according to the type and use. The project DIGIECOQUARRY intended to generate the information needed for the Quarry of the future or Quarry 4.0. For doing this, the interoperability between data source and the different tools and applications were considered as a must.

The size of the data, including the specific formats and the interdependency – connections between the sources – users – applications were defined during course of the project.

The data collected should be useful for one of the parties involved in the project not only for collecting, but for further quarrying and digitalization purposes.

The data produced as raw data due to intellectual property (IP) rights, would only be shared under some specific circumstances and for specific applications. The processed data and the results of the expert systems [solutions of the technology providers] were accessible and shared with the rest of the partners.

The naming, re-use, versions, metadata and standards to use were discussed. Also, the methods, software, sharing data tools as well as relevant software, associated documentation and repository were defined. More details can be found in WP4 deliverables.

Figure 2 shows all the requirements, constraints, regulations, guidelines that were analysed for the definition of the DIGIECOQUARRY data management methodology. The DIGIECOQUARRY data collection process and data management were built upon requirements and methodologies coming from several processes defined in WP1-5 or guidance rules (Open Access, GDPR, ETHICS).

Figure 2: Data management methodology in DIGIECOQUARRY.

3.2 Dataset categories

According to the project concept highlighted in Figure 1, this section describes project dataset categories (Table 1).

Table 1: DIGIECOQUARRY processes datasets general explanation and examples.

Data category	General explanation	Data types examples*
Site Preparation	The information about the terrain's physical characteristics exploitation, but also about enabling roads for the mobile equipment to access efficiently to all important points in the quarry.	3D map, images and videos, twin model, quarry map.
Extraction	It includes all the information of the processes carried out during the extraction: blast information, explosive information, fuel consumption, water consumption, quality of the material obtained.	Positioning (x,y,z) for drilling and explosives to be used, king and weight of explosives, litres of diesel, material quality measures: poor, medium, high, etc.
Loading & Internal Transportation	The information related to the process of loading mobile equipment from the extraction points to the treatment plant.	Distances, weight, cycle times, workers information, dumping position, hauling speed.
Treatment	The data processed here will consist of the production characteristics, the equipment performance statistics, the parameters used to control the production, lists of all consumables used in the process.	Tons of material, processing speed, capacity of the treatment (t/h), energy consumption (Kw), process configuration,
Storage	This will depend on the storage facilities if available on a quarry. Normally storage in the case of a quarry relates to the time spent on	Types of material stored, weight of the materials in storage, area used, reaming capacity, etc.

Data category	General explanation	Data types examples*
	loading and transporting the materials produced at the treatment plant to the customers.	
External Transport	In this data category, the data pertaining to the materials and external transportation facts including speed, distances, transporter facts, customer orders and receipts.	Material weight transported, monthly distribution, material type, etc...
Rehabilitation	The information on the backfilling of the quarry exploitation grounds is here handled.	Types of material used, backfilling volume, videos of the areas of the quarry that are being rehabilitated, the kind of operations to recover the environment, etc...
Business Management	This category will be using data from all processes in a quarry basically that will help the quarry owners and managers to get via helpful dashboards daily and historical information on how the quarry is performing in general: the production, the processes, the workers, the market, its financial performance, etc.	Material weight, costs, consumables, workers, finances, KPIs, etc.
Equipment	A very significant amount of information will be available thanks to the sensors that are now installed in most of the quarry equipment: for example drilling machines, treatment plants, trucks, cranes, etc....	The data types & formats are specified by each equipment provider.
Safety	In order to access the safety a lot of data from the other data categories can be used (e.g. equipment, sensor data). When there is no data available, we expect to install different types of sensors depending on the use case.	Working conditions of the system (running, running with limitations, on hold).

*: Only preliminary data types are mentioned. A complete description will be provided in D3.1 - List and characterisation of key data inputs due in M12.

3.2.1 Data of the project that may be impacted by the regulations

This section provides for each KTAs a first preliminary analysis of the usage of personal data. This analysis was completed according to regulation described in section 8.

- **Devices for automation of treatment plants and storage facilities**

Not applicable. There is no data in this area that may be subject to regulation issues.

- **Monitoring sensors and analysing tools for Mobile Machinery**

Some of the data involved under the regulation of the GDPR is the picture data. For tackling this issue, Abaut have already developed a sensor camera system able to generate, detect and blur the picture under the GDPR compliance. The picture data, in this case, is completely anonymous.

- **Mobile equipment & quarry geological deposit digitalisation & real-time modelling**

Not applicable. There is no data in this area that may be subject to regulation issues

- **BIM Management & Connection**

Any personal data was not involved. In case of any personal data involved, it was compliant to GDPR rules.

- **Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms**

In the case of the services/applications that were developed using artificial intelligence models, all data was anonymised in order to be compliant with GDPR, such as:

- Pilot workers personal information (names, personal identification data, etc.)
 - Images or videos that may include persons (by blurring faces)
 - Providers/external workers personal information

Moreover, the amount of personal information was the strictly minimal, needed to perform the analysis required by the models. In summary the principles described in section 8.1.3 were ensured.

- **Business management tool**

All data fields corresponding to personal data can be subject to regulations (in this case, for the business management tool). Examples of personal data, but not only, that are required to develop the business management tool are employee's data, customers data, partner companies or supplier data ... This type of personal data will follow the points and procedures described in *section Data Protection Regulation and Ethical Aspects* (and, if necessary, the deliverable "*D11.1 Ethics POPD Requirement*").

Some data that is processed by the business management tool may not be subjected to regulation. Some of these are still extremely sensitive data for the company (e.g., billing details data). This implies that security standards and protection measures must be taken into account to prevent unauthorized access to data or information leak.

- For the safety tool only the numbers of detected warnings and alerts were processed, stored or forwarded.

3.3 Data Collection and generation

Data collection and generation within this project can originate from any participating partner. The primary purpose of the collected data is to be analysed by expert systems. These systems, which are software tools, are designed to interpret and process the generated data, producing process-specific data required by other expert systems or applications. Depending on the source, data can either be manually collected or automatically generated through the project's technological infrastructure.

3.3.1.1 Manually Collected Data

Manual data collection occurred at the pilot sites (quarries) in cases where automated systems were not available or could not be implemented (e.g., tracking the amount and allocation of consumables over a specific period, fuel consumption, etc.). This manually collected data must be digitized in a predefined format (e.g., Excel tables, reports) to facilitate integration into the data lake and/or the IQS, ensuring it can be utilized by expert systems and other project partners.

The manual data collection process included all relevant information necessary for interpretation and analysis by consortium members. To ensure data protection and prevent the disclosure of confidential information, access to the data in the Data Lake adhered to the "need-to-know" principle.

The format, structure, and interdependencies of the manually collected data were thoroughly discussed and defined during the course of the project.

3.3.1.2 Data generated via the technological infrastructure of the project

Data generated through the technological infrastructure and digital tools is produced collaboratively by the project partners, leveraging their expert systems in coordination with the pilot sites. The generation, handling, presentation, and interpretation of this data are carried out jointly by the involved partners (e.g., Pilot Sites, Technology Providers, and Universities) to extract useful and meaningful insights.

This information is analysed in correlation with relevant processes and KPIs to support reporting. The requirements and characteristics of the data, including its formats and dependencies with automatically generated data, were established within WP3 (Identification of Key Data Inputs from Cyber & Physical Quarrying Systems and Development of Sensors, Automation, and Process Control).

3.3.1.3 Data types and formats

Due to the different technologies applied, DIGIECOQUARRY created and modified at least these data formats according to the sources

- Processed data resulting from the Expert Systems and Pilot Sites
 - Numerical
 - Alphanumerical
 - Images & Maps
 - Dates
- Possible format of the files
 - CSV
- Excel (also in open data format)
 - JPEG
 - Word (also in open data format)
 - PDF
 - Vector (point, line (or arc), and polygon data)
 - Raster (grid data)
- IFC (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Industry_Foundation_Classes)

The data was made accessible to the quarry sites for data visualization for integration, and subsequent processes and to the expert systems [and other applications] for further processing.

3.3.2 Sharepoint of the project (Teams)

During this project, DIGIECOQUARRY used SharePoint for sharing different files and documents and for schedule meetings according to the different working packages [WP] and tasks [T].

The layout of SharePoint goes as follows.

The main accessing application could be Teams or SharePoint. Through Teams it can be observed the different layout in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Teams data sharing platform and organization in DIGIECOQUARRY.

The project used Teams as daily communication channel and SharePoint as file repository which helps for finding and sharing the different documents.

3.4 Data flows

The data flows implemented within the architecture of the Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS) are illustrated in Figure 4. These flows outline the pathways through which data is collected, processed, and disseminated across the system, ensuring seamless integration and functionality.

Figure 4: Data Architecture.

Sensors send their data to their connected peers, referred to as sub-platforms in Figure 4. The latter involve the communication needed and the data acquisition processes to further classify the data in a local server. These platforms may be accessed directly to show data.

Sensors transmit their data to connected systems, referred to as "sub-platforms" in the figure. These sub-platforms manage the communication and data acquisition processes, classifying the data locally on a server. They can also provide direct access to display data as needed.

Each sub-platform transmits optimized and pre-processed data to the main platform of the IQS. This main platform is implemented as a Data Lake, capable of storing and organizing incoming data in various formats.

In certain cases, depending on the sensors deployed in the field, an IoT platform in the cloud may be required to collect data, functioning similarly to the sub-platforms described earlier. For clarity, these sub-platforms will be referred to as "Expert Systems" throughout the chapter.

The IoT platform also transmits its refined data to the Data Lake, creating a global repository of all data related to a single quarry. Although the figure does not display data derived from manual inputs or quarry databases, these sources also contribute to the overall system.

The Data Lake data is accessible to the BIM, the AI services and the Business Management Tools (application) at the upper level. The higher-level structure of the data warehouse will be divided into separated data repositories for each quarry Data Lake (Pilot sites in the project).

3.5 DIGIECOQUARRY components involved in digitalisation

To comprehend the data architecture at a high level, we will refer to the schema displayed in Figure 5. The data sources include:

Live Readings: Data is collected in real-time or at discrete intervals from sensors deployed across the quarry.

Data Loggers: Installed on various equipment, primarily mobile units, these loggers temporarily store data to mitigate challenges arising from poor connectivity often encountered in quarry environments.

This architecture ensures continuous and reliable data collection, even in conditions with limited network coverage, and supports the seamless integration of data into the overall system.

Figure 5: Data Architecture schema for DIGIECOQUARRY.

3.5.1.1 BIM

BIM (Building Information Modelling) is the process based on virtual model that simulates all aspects of the project and contains information on the characteristics of each building components. The BIM process itself last for all project lifecycle from design phase through the construction, management, maintenance, reconstruction, and demolishing. BIM is a very effective technology in terms of representing virtually a model that can be used for a very wide number of applications around almost any industrial activity.

In the case of DIGIECOQUARRY, as of September 2021, the project is defining the functionalities that will be implemented within a BIM quarry model, in order to monitor the different processes of a quarry, as well as integrate disconnected systems and workflows that need to tie together in Common Data Environment (CDE). The ultimate goal is the production of a Digital Twin which is a virtual representative of the project. The first step in terms of data processing is the extraction of the physical dimensions in 3D of the quarry in order to build a model that can be used to access the different physical locations of the quarry (navigating a map), that could hold each a model that will deliver information about the processes data. Therefore, the BIM is a very handy user tool incorporating attractive and realistic quarry features in a form of a Digital Twin.

BIM maturity levels range from Level 0-3 and beyond, that defines which criteria are required to be consider in a specified way. The UK maturity model is displayed in Figure 6: BIM maturity level. In the case of DIGIECOQUARRY, BIM Level 3 was implemented. BIM level 3 is a single collaborative, interoperable, online, project model with construction sequencing (4D), cost (5D), and project lifecycle information (6D and 7D) and is intended to deliver better business outcomes.

Figure 6: BIM Maturity level.

Figure 7: Example of a BIM model for a Quarry exploitation front.

BIM is thus mainly in this case a data consumer that need information coming from different sources as displayed in Figure 4. As an example of the functionalities that could be introduced in the DEQ BIM, an extract of actual applications in the building industry (<https://www.buildingsmart.es>) is presented in Table 2 that focuses on the process management of a BIM model. The explanations were tuned to meet the quarry processes.

Table 2: BIM Features.

Nr.	Service/Use Case	Explanation on the Data that is handled
1	Record Modelling (RM)	This has potential to contain information regarding not only the main architectural and physical elements, but equipment and asset information as well. The record model may contain information regarding design specifications allowing for validation that the as-constructed BIMs meets or exceeds these specifications. Furthermore, with the continuous improvement of the record model and the capability to store more information, the model contains a true representation of space with information such as serial numbers, warranties the components in the quarry.
2	As Constructed Modelling	A process in which BIMs contain an accurate depiction of the physical conditions and environment of a facility and its assets.
3	Asset Management (AM)	The assets included in BIM(s), consisting of the physical building, systems, surrounding environment, and equipment, must be maintained, upgraded, and operated at an efficiency which will satisfy both the owner and users at the lowest appropriate cost. It assists in financial decision-making, as well as short-term and long-term planning are also supported by the BIM(s).
4	Space Management and Tracking	A process in which BIM(s) are utilized to effectively allocate, manage, and track assigned workspaces and resources.
5	Maintenance & Repair Information	A process to allow the collection and storage of maintenance and repair information about objects to be brought into BIM(s).
6	Facility Management Documentation	A process where a facility data schema is developed to ensure information is supplied to the BIM(s) in electronic form so that it can be easily exchanged between the BIM(s) and the organizations selected IWMS tool.
7	Disaster Planning / Emergency Preparedness (DRC)	A process in which emergency responders would have access to critical building information in the form of BIM(s). The BIM(s) would provide critical building information to the responders, that would improve the efficiency of the response and, more importantly, minimize the safety risks.
8	Security Management	A process to identify and evaluate the security zones in the facility using BIM(s). The evaluation ensures that there are no "leaks" in the security strategy.

Nr.	Service/Use Case	Explanation on the Data that is handled
9	Communication move/add/change management (CM)	A process tying the BIM(s) to personnel management to help ensure that communications will be in place for all workers. This item also ensures that hard wired computers are operational when a person is in office space a quarry.
10	Way finding (WF)	A process of using the BIM(s) for documenting and aiding facility or site workers. Wayfinding encompasses all the ways in which people and machines orient themselves in the physical space and navigate from place to place.
11	Risk Management	A process to identify some issues that can be prevented by establishing data-driven analysis and simulations of potential disruptions. This analysis requires structured data sets provided by intelligent BIM(s)
12	Energy Efficiency	A process in which BIM can be used to help reduce annual energy use and minimize environmental risks
13	Common Data Environment (CDE)	A process of tying together various disconnected systems and workflows, and enables handover between all the participants in facility's lifecycle: architects, engineers, contractors, operators, facility managers, commissioning agents, etc.
14	Digital Twin	Refers to a digital replica of physical assets, processes, people, places, systems and devices that can be used for various purposes. The digital representation provides both the elements and the dynamics of how an Internet of Things device operates and lives throughout its life cycle.

Data was fed to the BIM SW (IFC) normally through the data lake that will gather basically all data coming from the quarries. Data within the BIM needed to be protected from unauthorized users and to follow strict data access and management standards as used for any web-based application nowadays.

3.5.1.2 Expert Systems

The expert systems are digital systems able to generate, read and process data according to the area of expertise [e.g., at the processing plant, BIM, etc] intended to be analysed during the project. The idea is to use the systems and tools already developed by each partner, in case that these tools already exist, to avoid redundancies in analytics tools and to focus in the areas and/or results that needs to be developed. The expert systems provide the necessary processed information for the creation of added value application between the different partners.

- **Mobile Equipment Digitalization (2 different data models)**

The characteristics of the expert systems related to mobile machinery are shown in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3: Mobile Equipment Expert System Data Features (ABAUT).

PROVIDER		ABAUT SOLUTION
Nr.	Service/Use Case	Explanation on the data that is handled
1	Mobile Machinery –Loading & Transport (ABAUT)	The traceability of the material provides a deep knowledge of the quality and quantity of the material extracted for a correct processing and analysing at the processing plant storage, and internal transportation (the information can be crosscheck with the geological rock quality and material behaviour and grade, together with their impact on the other subsequent mining processes).

		<p>To follow the mass-flow through out different sites in the quarry, it's necessary to refer to underline map giving information on the mining area (processing plant, extraction area, blasting fields, workshop, storage facilities, gas-station...) that would consequently correlate with the BIM of the mine.</p> <p>For the external transportation, is possible to follow the transport from the quarry to the customer. Data for customer, material, quantity may be retrieved from the central system or generated by visual logistic recognition services.</p>
2	Integrated management of the trucks fleet, including environment & safety aspects.	<p>The integrated fleet management system and analytics includes not only the availability of the machines, but it is also connected with the machine utilization and their maintenance plant as well as with the production and daily plan.</p> <p>For increasing the performance of the fleet, it is possible to set different dashboards and analytics for the energy needed to carry out the different machine activities. This tool improves the performance, reducing the energy needed and the environmental impact of the activities.</p> <p>Also, a correct maintenance plan and the implementation of best practices will reduce the supply chain regularity, the use of spare parts, and the energy and time needed to perform different machine activities can be reduced.</p> <p>In specific areas, stationary cameras can be installed for detecting the presence of people within the viewing range of the camera. Same applies for the cameras installed on the mobile mining equipment. To detect the presence of people and their proximity to machines, based on sensors.</p> <p>This report generation can bring a deep knowledge of the current activities and processes for a better decision-making step and operational performance.</p>
3	Automatic generation of the documents of the materials	<p>The automatic generation of documents and reports suppose an automation of certain activities carried out every day by the different operators (as an example working hours, production, activities report will save time for the operators and will also create standardization of the data for the different implementations in several other systems/services. This report generation can bring a deep knowledge of the current activities and processes for a better decision-making step and operational performance.</p>

Table 4: Mobile Equipment Expert System Data Features (DH&P).

PROVIDER		DH&P
Nr.	Service/Use Case	Explanation on the Data that is handled
1	Input data from mobile equipment (with focus on loading/hauling)	<p>The expert system smartQuarry relies on input from mobile machinery data to obtain multiple integrated analysis about the dynamic mining process and performance. The input data is gathered from sensors equipped directly by the equipment manufactures and as well as a set of additional retrofit sensors. The transmission and connection between sensors and a central installed data logger is managed with a CAN bus. The data is transmitted from the central data logger via mobile network or WLAN to a central server and IOT analyse platform. All data is provided with a time stamp that allows the full historical monitoring of the performance of each equipment. The expert system commonly records OEM pressure, flow and multiple engine and operator monitoring sensor values combined with retrofit DGPS, load cells, fuel sensors or tire pressure sensors etc. From there the basic machine outputs are monitored and displayed such as:</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Operating status ▪ Position ▪ Operating, working and idle times ▪ Utilization ▪ Driving distances, speeds, elevation travelled ▪ Fuel consumption ▪ Production performance (tonnage moved) ▪ Maintenance parameters (tire pressure, oil temperatures etc.)
2	Integrated data of the fleet management, performance and material tracking	<p>All data gathered from the mobile equipment is processed and stored in a structured manner and integrated in the platform smartQuarry/AutoPLAN. The platform is a complex hub for data visualization, analysis and the data integration of additional inputs from the quarry management such as topographical and geological information. Focus must be laid on the combination of automatically obtained equipment data, manual inputs and existing models for the terrain and deposit.</p> <p>Combined with additional model data such as material types, 3D geofences and online material analysis data a detail material tracking from the mining face to the pre-crusher can be realized. In combination with data from the treatment process the geological knowledge of the deposit is enhanced allowing a sustainable use of the specific resource and a controlled quality management.</p> <p>The integration of manual inputs together with the automatically obtained machine data allows also the adaptability of the system for example for maintenance management of the fleet. In the DEQ project the focus is on the control of the full production cycle, controlling and enhancing process performance, environmental and H&S benefits.</p>
3	Automatic generation of the documents of the materials	<p>The system offers multiple web services with personalized log-in. The services combine map visualization, customizable dash boards for machine parameter analysis and KPIs or fleet maintenance plans. The service includes a reporting service where customized reports can be downloaded or transmitted to defined parties on a regular basis. The system is customizable depending on the different needs of the specific quarry operation.</p>

- **Treatment Plant Digitalization expert system**

The expert system related to treatment plant is shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Treatment Plant Expert System Data Features (ARCO).

Nr.	Service/Use Case	Explanation on the Data that is handled
1	Input data from machinery sensor.	<p>The expert system gets data from the main machinery through the sensor installed. The sensor can work under analogical or digital system besides connect through Modbus.</p> <p>The most used types of sensors are:</p> <p>Kilowatt meters, toroidal transformers, load cell, radar and video including frequency converters.</p>

		<p>This information will be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Energy measure: From individual important machinery as mill, screw, feeder, or main part of the treatment: primary, secondary, ... ▪ Production: It is possible to know the commodity that each part produces through the weigh bridges, continuous weighs, radar or video. ▪ Waste: It is the same case that production. ▪ Time off, time load...
2	Integrated data	<p>The different input data give a lot of information about the treatment process, production, performance, storage, energy, difference process time, safety even forecasts.</p> <p>Regarding this information, the expert system offers several outputs, for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Production of different elements consumed and important times. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Control at all safety elements, warning, alerts, power drops, time down, maintenance, full/empty warehouse. <p>It must be pointed the quantity of data that is necessary to save into the expert system and how much is stored in the data lake or IQS.</p>
3	Automatic generation of the documents of the materials.	<p>The system generates automatically datasheet with statistics, it can work out data list too, which including time starting, time stopping, time down, power drops, performance, wastes, production...</p> <p>This information can be used by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Technical staff. ▪ Plant director. ▪ Managers. ▪ Supplier. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Internal and external transport. ▪ Storage.

▪ **BIM Expert Systems**

The characteristics of the BIM expert system are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: BIM Expert Systems Data Features (APP).

Nr.	Service/Use Case	Explanation on the Data that is handled
1	Ecodomus – Project Lifecycle BIM	EcoDomus is the leading expert system for project lifecycle BIM, that provides a 'Common Data Environment (CDE)' for all relevant types of information. It gives a 3D view of facilities in an easy-to-use format that links the Asset Information Model (in BIM) with real-time facility operations data acquired by meters and sensors (Building Management Systems, BMS) and facility management (FM) software. This allows for intelligent analysis of a building's performance and supports better

		maintenance practices, resulting in significant reductions in labour hours and energy use.
2	Elecosoft - Powerproject BIM	Powerproject is an Enterprise Project, Portfolio, Resource and Cost Management & 4D Planning software solution for organizations that manage people working across multiple projects, programmes and project portfolios.
3	Trimble TILOS	Linear project management solution provides a simplified, visual look at your construction project through a powerful linear scheduling view.
4	Deltek - Acumen Suite	Acumen Suite is a comprehensive Project Analytics, Diagnostics, Risk Analysis, Forecast Solutions and visualization and problem resolution platform.

▪ **Safety Expert System for Processing Plants**

The characteristics of the expert system related to safety in processing plants are described in Table 7.

Table 7: Safety Expert System Data Features (ITK).

Nr.	Service/Use Case	Explanation on the Data that is handled
1	Safety Tool	<p>The safety management system for stationary equipment is a system that aims to reduce the risks of a collision between persons and machines and hence helps to achieve vision zero (zero accidents at construction sites)</p> <p>Based on the example of a scrapper system, sensors will be selected which shall detect objects (including machines and persons) coming close or interfering with the machine. The system shall then, based on rules (e.g. on classification rules) start measures to avoid harm (e.g. start with a noise/light alarm up until an emergency stop).</p> <p>Data to predict traffic (e.g. trucks) might come from a different expert system (e.g. 1 or 2).</p>

▪ **Plant simulation tool**

The characteristics of the plant simulation tool are shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Plant simulation tool (Roctim).

Nr.	Service/Use Case	Explanation on the Data that is handled
1	Plant simulation tool - Plantsmith	<p>The plant simulation tool allows users to draw their plant and set up all machines to simulate and calculate environmental effects as well as production. Different set-ups and configurations will give different results so that the user can elaborate with the tool to find a good setting. It can also interact with sensor data and do calculations on the sensor data as well.</p> <p>Calculations from simulation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Energy and production ▪ Plant and equipment utilization ▪ Enviromental effects

3.5.1.3 Data lake, IoT Platform and Data warehouse

The data lake is centralized and secured repository, by quarry, based on the cloud, to allow, in particular, the ingestion, the storage, the analysis and the usage of relevant data, available in its native format, such as structured or unstructured files but also databases, coming from each quarry (pilot sites) as well as from the technical providers partners working with them (Figure 8). These cloud data lakes are fully administrable to enable right accesses and give appropriate permissions. Data lake users (pilot site users, BIM, AI & data warehouse, IoT devices, expert systems), once authenticated and authorized, are able to:

- Create, Read, Update, Delete data (download/upload), according to data lake specifications
- Explore data lake content
- Share BIM, AI models and expert system data
- Store:
 - Files, Images (txt, xml, csv, json, zip, jpeg, xls...) with associated metadata
 - Data bases (SQL, NO SQL)
 - Events (IoT data, sensors data)

Figure 8: Data Lake global architecture.

The IoT platform builds an IoT eco-system of objects of the physical world. It allows the digital representation of the devices on the quarry field. For that, it gathers data from the sensors and the expert systems. The IoT platform also enable the development of applications using data from IoT data sources. These applications cover all the mining processes: Blasting, Drilling, Loading & Transport, Storage, Treatment and Transport. The created applications enable services that support the smart, sustainable and digital quarry. E.g. H&S, Efficiency, selectivity & profitability, environmental impact, social acceptance, autonomous/remote operations, process control, advanced analytics, etc.

IoT data are sent and shared securely in real time (if needed) and with low latency to generate insights and actions to help improve business and processes. Figure 9 illustrates the IoT core subsystems generally needed for the implementation of Thing, Insight and Actions concepts.

Core Subsystems

Figure 9: IoT Core subsystems and main principles.

The Data warehouse mainly aims to analyse data. The data warehouse extracts data from the data lake that are needed fundamentally for Business Intelligence and Artificial Intelligence services. The data warehouse also gather the results of data processing implemented by the AI algorithms: data in this case have a well-defined structure and organization in order to be retrieved by the applications dashboard easily following specific data construction models and APIs.

3.5.1.4 Artificial Intelligence algorithm applications

The Artificial Intelligence services that were developed in the project were fed with the data coming principally from the data lake and data warehouse framework as shown in Figure 5. The results of the algorithms are also stored in the data warehouse in such a way that the DIGIECOQUARRY application dashboard composed of the IQS high level services.

Table 9 containing the AI services is shown explaining what type of data and results are being pursued.

Table 9: Data characteristics tied to the services that will be developed using Artificial Intelligence algorithms.

Nr.	Service/Use Case	Explanation on the Data that is handled
1	Risks Detection (RIQ)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Risk identification and detection of a possible accident in the quarry characterizing the risk levels, possible locations.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inputs used to detect risks: Human factors, weather, environment and equipment
2	Metaquarry: Advanced information search on Quarries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using PLN processing, the service via keywords is able to look for specialized information on the quarry infrastructure, processes, business and workers. Data is looked upon the data lake, specific quarry and equipment providers databases and the Internet in general. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The data formats may comprise textual or any audio-visual type.
3	PrMa: Predictive Maintenance (AM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using data coming from the quarry equipment sensors through the data lake, PrMA is able to detect anomalies on the day-to-day operation of the quarry machines and equipment. PrMa predicts several equipment/machine characteristics such as future repair needs, end-of-life time intervals, possible solutions to a detected problem, etc.
4	StockForecast: Stock handling and management functions	The StockForecast service handles production and market information in order to advice and inspect how the stock management of a quarry is being and should be performed.
5	Hawkeye: Quarry visual inspection using AI image processing	Hawkeye basically processes image information provided by cameras, images coming from drones and satellite imaging in order to display quarry information about its surface analysing changes, providing guidance about material quality, point of extraction historical data and advices on future choices for points of extraction.

3.5.1.5 Business management tools

These tools require a very significant amount of information coming from all the infrastructure of quarry and players. Specially for example the static information coming from each and every quarry providing detailed information about their business figures. As main interface the business management tool uses the data warehouse to extract all needed information (Table 10).

Table 10: Data characteristics tied to the services provided by the business management tool.

Nr.	Service/Use Case	Explanation on the data that is handled
1	Aggregated data visualization	Main quarry KPIs are here accessed divided by the quarry processes: from the site preparation activities till the rehabilitation
2	Energy Consumption	Here all the quarry elements that are used for the production are considered and that may incur in energy consumption. The latter used for production specially.
3	Load and Transport cycles	Analysis of the product volumes handled per transport cycle
4	Total inventory by site and forecast	Here the number of different products handled in a quarry, their production levels forecasts and sales will be displayed
5	Report by photography (mobile phone)	Photos can be uploaded to the datawarehouse from different points of the quarry by the workers in order to analyse possible risks, needed activities to be performed on the roads, maintenance of machines, etc...
6	Productivity Assessment	Productivity will be measured by showing a machine, factory or person efficiency in converting inputs into useful outputs.

7	Work Environment & Worker Management	Workforce detailed information will be here displayed in order to access easily statistic ABOUT KPIs that involve the workers performance, quarry working conditions, health and security information, etc.
8	Financial Management	All important financial statistics are here accessed in terms of monetary transactions fundamentally.
9	Quality Management	Quality KPIs will be here displayed considering each process quality measures and how the quality controls are being performed in the quarry.
10	Environmental control	A dashboard will be provided and will show basically the emission of all different gases and particles that are emitted within a quarry. Also, it will cover KPIs on how the environment is being taking care of within the quarry, displaying relevant statistics about waste, resources expenditure, handling of dangerous products, etc.
11	Water Management	Basically, the water consumption, use and recycling will be here analysed.
12	Waste Management	KPIs with respect of all sources of waste and how it is handled in a quarry is here displayed
13	Maintenance Operations	Here statistics about the maintenance operation performed and needed can be observed, including costs.

4 DIGIECOQUARRY shared dataset description

4.1 Potential datasets / description

This section provides guidelines for the description of the different types of datasets to be collected and shared by DIGIECOQUARRY after the end of the project with respect to Open Access to scientific publications which aims to improve and maximize access to and re-use of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects and needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications .

The descriptions of the different datasets, including their reference, file format, standards and metadata and archiving and preservation to be used are given in Table 11.

Table 11: DIGIECOQUARRY Dataset description template.

Dataset Reference	Each dataset has an identifier that is generated by the combination of the name of the project, the pilot site, the use case in which it is generated and the datatype: "DIGIECOQUARRY_Pilot-Site_Dataprovider and ExpertSystem".
Dataset Name	Name of the dataset.
Dataset Description	Each dataset has a full data description explaining the data provenance, origin and usefulness. Reference may be made to existing data that could be reused.
Standards and metadata	The metadata attributes list to be used to explore the dataset.
File format / data format	Standard file type of the log file for example csv, xml, jpeg Type of formatting of the payload of a log item, for example: binary, txt, json Structure and definition of log parameters that can be logged in a log item
Data Sharing (access right and License)	Explanation of the sharing policies related to the dataset between the next options: Open: Open for public disposal. Embargo: It will become public when the embargo period applied by the publisher is over. In case it is categorized as embargo, the end date of the embargo period must be written in DD/MM/YYYY format. Restricted: Only for project internal use. Each dataset must have its distribution license. Provide information about personal data and mention if the data is anonymized or not. Indicate if the dataset entails personal data and how this issue is taken into account. License: Example of type of licenses (cf. https://opendefinition.org/licenses/)
Archiving and Preservation	The preservation guarantee and the data storage during and after the project (for example databases, institutional repositories, public repositories, etc.).

5 Open access to scientific publications and underlying research data

DIGIECOQUARRY has agreed to provide open access to scientific publications and the underlying research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications according to article 29.2. DIGIECOQUARRY uses the specific Horizon 2020 guidelines associated with open access¹ to ensure that the results of the project provide the greatest impact possible.

DIGIECOQUARRY ensures the open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results and provides access to the research data needed to validate the results presented in deposited scientific publications.

The following lists the minimum fields of metadata that come with a DIGIECOQUARRY project-generated scientific publication in a repository:

- The terms: “European Union (EU)”, “Horizon 2020”
- Name of the action (Research and Innovation Action)
- Acronym and grant number (DIGIECOQUARRY, 101003750)
- Publication date
- Length of embargo period if applicable
- Persistent identifier

When referencing open access data, DIGIECOQUARRY includes, at a minimum, the following statement demonstrating EU support (with relevant information included into the repository metadata):

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101003750”.

In regard to the specific repositories available to the DIGIECOQUARRY consortium, some project partners maintain institutional repositories, where project scientific publications and in some instances, research data were deposited. The use of a specific repository depends primarily on the primary creator of the publication and on the data in question.

Other project partners do not operate publicly accessible institutional repositories. When depositing scientific publications, they use either a domain specific repository or use the EU recommended service OpenAIRE (<https://www.openaire.eu/>) as an initial step to finding resources to determine relevant repositories.

Project research data was deposited to the online data repository ZENODO. It is a free service developed by CERN under the EU FP7 project OpenAIRE plus (grant agreement no. 283595).

The repository also includes information regarding the software, tools and instruments that were used by the dataset creator(s) so that secondary data users can access and then validate the results.

The DIGIECOQUARRY data collections are accessed in ZENODO repository at a <https://zenodo.org/communities/digiecoquarry>

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/open-access_en.htm

In summary, as a baseline, DIGIECOQUARRY beneficiaries deposited:

- Scientific publications – on their respective institute repositories in addition (when relevant) to the DIGIECOQUARRY ZENODO repository
- Research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications ('underlying data') to the DIGIECOQUARRY ZENODO repository.

Recently, the European Commission launched an open publication platform², for publishing scientific articles that are accessible to all. The platform showcases the results of research funded by Horizon Europe, the EU's research and innovation program for the period 2021-2027, and its predecessor, Horizon 2020. Open Research Europe provides free access to the latest scientific discoveries for all, researchers and citizens alike. It provides a direct solution to the major difficulties often associated with publishing scientific results, including delays, barriers to re-use of results and high costs. The platform is an optional service offered to Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 beneficiaries, so that they can meet their funding needs for immediate open access, at no cost to them. DIGIECOQUARRY beneficiaries considered the usage of this platform or any other solution to ensure the open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications.

² <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/about>

6 FAIR data management principles

In the context of Open-Access to scientific information described in article 29.2, the data underlying publications that are shared were FAIR³, that is, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. These requirements do not affect implementation choices and do not necessarily suggest any specific technology, standard, or implementation solution.

The FAIR principles were generated to improve the practices for data management and data curation, and FAIR aims to describe the principles in order to be applied to a wide range of data management purposes, whether it is data collection or data management of larger research projects regardless of scientific disciplines.

With the endorsement of the FAIR principles by H2020 and their implementation in the guidelines for H2020, the FAIR principles serve as a template for data lifecycle management and ensure that the most important components for lifecycle are covered.

This is intended as an implementation of the FAIR concept rather than a strict technical implementation of the FAIR principles. DIGIECOQUARRY will implement several actions described below to carry on the FAIR principles.

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

- The datasets have very rich metadata to facilitate the findability. Open data formats (csv, xml) were used.
- All the datasets have Digital Object Identifiers provided by the public repository (ZENODO).
- The reference used for the dataset follows a format like the following: "DIGIECOQUARRY_Pilot-Site_Dataprovider -- ExpertSystem".

Making data openly accessible:

- The datasets are available using a public repository (e.g. ZENODO) after the project.
- No software is needed to access the data.
- The data and their associated metadata were deposited in a public repository or in an institutional repository.

Making data interoperable:

- Open and widely used data formats in quarry sector (csv, jpeg, IFC, xml, json) were used. This list will be updated.

Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

- The data producers made their data available for third parties within public repositories. The data are reused for the scientific publications' validation purpose.
- Data producers can license their data to allow the widest reuse possible. Examples of licenses are available at <https://opendefinition.org/licenses/>.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/open-access_en.htm

7 Allocation of resources

The costs to make the data FAIR in DIGIECOQUARRY were handled by each partner willing to generate and share its data.

In the project, each beneficiary had a Data Manager who liaises with the PTC (Project Technical Coordination) / WPT (Work Package Team) about data management issues.

Scientific publications and the underlying research data collected as part of this project and needed to validate the results are owned by the data producers or partners involved in the pilot sites. The partners take the responsibility for the collection, management, and sharing of the research data. Data quality assessment was the responsibility of each pilot site.

8 Data Protection Regulation and Ethical Aspects

8.1 GDPR Application in DIGIECOQUARRY

8.1.1 Background

Data protection is both a central issue for research ethics in Europe and a fundamental human right. It is intimately linked to autonomy and human dignity, and the principle that everyone should be valued and respected.

The protection of personal data in the European Union is guaranteed by Article 8 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (CFR) and Article 16 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU).

In the era of technical development progress and innovations, more and more information and personal data is digitalized and can be retrieved more easily and quickly. Therefore, the informational self-determination of EU citizens is both important and challenging. The abundance of information and the ease of its storage and combination, awakes desires and carries high risks. Data protection is intended to counter these risks preventively.

To meet the new challenges, the EU recently has introduced the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) which is directly applicable in the EU countries since 2018 and replaces the previous Data Protection Directive.

DIGIECOQUARRY developed systems, technologies and processes for integrated digitisation and automation real-time process control, to be piloted in 5 EU quarries with the target of improving health and safety conditions for workers. The pilot tests led to improved efficiency of processes, maximizing quarry resources and sustainable management of water, energy emissions, minimised environmental impact and expanding the EU aggregates and construction business. Coupling Artificial Intelligence approaches with cyber-physical systems and the Internet of Things concept, made Industry 4.0 approach possible and the smart sustainable extractive site a reality.

To achieve the research and development of such integrated digitisation and automation real-time process control systems and processes, personal data were collected and processed.

The DEQ Consortium was fully aware of this and its related challenges in terms of research ethics and, more specifically, data protection.

In the next section we analyse the essential elements of the GDPR for its application in the DIGIECOQUARRY project.

8.1.2 Key concepts and definitions

The GDPR defines some terms that are relevant to data protection in DEQ:

- **Personal data** means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person who can be identified, directly or indirectly, by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural, or social identity of that natural person (Art. 4 GDPR).
- **Special categories of personal data** are personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership [...] as well as genetic data, biometric data

for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation (Art. 9 GDPR).

- **Processing** means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure, or destruction (Art. 4 GDPR).
- **Profiling** means any form of automated processing of personal data consisting of the use of personal data to evaluate certain personal aspects relating to a natural person, to analyse or predict aspects concerning that natural person's performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences, interests, reliability, behaviour, location, or movements (Art. 4 GDPR).
- **Anonymisation:** a process of ensuring that the risk of somebody being identified in the data is negligible.
- **Pseudonymisation** means the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person (Art. 4 GDPR).
- **Risk based approach:** data protection must be proportionate to the risks to data subjects.
- **Consent of the data subject** means any freely given, specific, informed, and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her.
- **Controller** means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency, or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data [...] (Art. 4 GDPR).
- **Processor** means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency, or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller (Art. 4 GDPR).

8.1.3 Data protection principles

Regarding data protection according to GDPR, there are seven basic principles (Figure 10) that must be respected when collecting and processing personal data in DEQ (see Art. 5 GDPR):

Personal data must be processed lawfully. The consent to the storage and processing of personal data must be voluntary, specific, unambiguous, and based on information. Personal data must be processed fairly and, in a manner understandable to the data subject. The principle of transparency assumes that all information is easily accessible and understandable and written in clear and simple language.

- **Purpose Limitation**

Personal data must be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and must not be further processed in a way incompatible with those purposes. Further processing for archiving scientific research purposes shall not be incompatible with the initial purposes if it is in accordance with Article 89.1 GDPR.

- **Data Minimisation**

Personal data must be adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary for the purposes of the processing. Personal data should be allowed to be processed only if the purpose of the processing cannot reasonably be achieved by other means.

- **Accuracy**

Personal data must be accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date. All reasonable steps shall be taken to ensure that personal data which are inaccurate for the purposes of their processing are erased or rectified without delay.

- **Storage Limitation**

Personal data must be stored so that it allows data subjects not to be identified longer than necessary for the purposes for which they are processed. Exception: Personal data may be retained for longer periods, to the extent that the personal data are used exclusively for scientific and non-commercial purposes in accordance with Article 89.1 GDPR subject to the implementation of appropriate technical and organisational measures required by the GDPR to protect the rights and freedoms of the data subject.

- **Integrity and Confidentiality**

Personal data must be processed in a manner which ensures adequate security of personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage using appropriate technical or organisational measures.

- **Accountability**

The controller shall be responsible for and be able to prove compliance with the above principles and GDPR requirements.

8.2 An approach to comply with GDPR in DIGIECOQUARRY

8.2.1 Data Usage in DEQ

All data processed within the framework of DEQ complied with the data protection principles described above. All beneficiaries involved in DEQ adhered to these principles. DEQ essentially collected mandatory data to support its research activities.

All consortium members have agreed that DEQ participants' personal data were safeguarded as follows:

- No unnecessary data collection activities were performed within the project's lifetime.
- Personal data that have been collected for analysis were handled discretely and with anonymity.
- No personal data was collected without definite permission of the human participants.
- Every personal data collected throughout the project was treated with respect to the protection of fundamental human rights (e.g., separating general and personal data, handling encrypted personal data and identities, erasing irrelevant personal data).
- The participants were granted with the right to access their personal data and the analysis and user models made based on it.

Compliance with data protection principles such as data minimisation were guaranteed prior to data collection and processing.

8.2.2 Data Protection in Collection and Processing

Within the DEQ project, there are several partners who collected and process personal data of different kinds and from different sources. Each pilot site named its own Data controller and data processor in order to collect and process the data.

Controllers are the main decision-makers. They exercise overall control over the purposes and means of the processing of personal data. Processors act on behalf of, and only on the instructions of the controller. The processor should only process personal data in line with the controller's instructions.

The controller must comply with and prove compliance with all the data protection principles. He or she will be responsible for the compliance of the processor.

It is important that each partner is individually responsible for compliance with current legislation. This includes their personal responsibility to carry out their tasks in a way that ensures compliance with the DEQ approach of data protection by design and by default.

In some cases, it is likely that the processing of personal data in DEQ raises risks concerning ethics and data protection, e.g., the processing of sensitive health data of employees or the usage of new technologies as automated data collection with electronic devices, profiling, tracking or the combination of data from different sources.

To counter and mitigate these risks, ethical and legal issues were identified and analysed. A questionnaire on ethics and data protection was sent to each partner so that they can identify these aspects. The template for this questionnaire was available as an annex to D 11.1.

Appropriate technical and organizational measures were taken in advance of data collection and processing. These could be for example:

- the pseudonymisation or anonymisation of personal data.
- data minimisation.
- applied cryptography (e.g., encryption and hashing).
- using data-protection focused service providers and storage platforms. Arrangements that enable data subjects to exercise their fundamental rights, e.g., access to their personal data and consent to its use or transfer.

Each data controller must keep a record of the processing activities for which he or she is responsible (accountability principle) including adequate documentation on what personal data are processed, how, to what purpose, how long; documented processes and procedures aiming at tackling data protection issues at an early state when building information systems or responding to a data breach; the purposes of the processing, a description of the categories of data and recipients of the data and a general description of the technical and organizational safeguard measures. The documentation obligations depend on the risks posed by the nature of the processing of personal data.

In accordance with the provisions of article 30 of the GDPR, the basic content of the records to be considered compliant with the documentation and accountability obligations, must have at least the following information:

- Name and contact details of the controller and, where applicable, the joint controller, the controller's representative and the data protection officer;
- Purposes of the processing;
- Description of the categories of data subjects and of the categories of personal data;
- The categories of recipients to whom the personal data have been or will be disclosed including recipients in third countries or international organisations;
- Where applicable, transfers of personal data to a third country or an international organisation, including the identification of that third country or international organisation and, in the case of transfers referred to in the second subparagraph of Article 49(1) GDPR, the documentation of suitable safeguards;
- Where possible, the envisaged time limits for erasure of the different categories of data;

- here possible, a general description of the technical and organisational security measures referred to in Article 32(1) GDPR.

The controllers and processors are provided with some record templates in Annex 0.

Different methods of assessing the impact on data protection and privacy could be used to support the implementation of the essential requirements laid down in the GDPR.

To assure data protection and security of the research and to reduce risks and discomfort for the participants, necessary measures must be implemented which contain, inter alia, the following points:

- **Informed consent:** Informed consent is required for data collection, data storage, data processing and publication of raw or processed data. Before consent is sought, information must be given, specifying the alternatives, risks, and benefits for those involved, in a way users understand.
- **Voluntary participation:** Participation is on a voluntary basis.
- **Minimal risk:** Participants should not be exposed to more than minimal risk. The data would be retained for the shortest period necessary to achieve the project objectives.
- **Anonymity:** Volunteers have the right to remain anonymous. All data analyses are performed on an anonymous basis. It is very difficult to create completely anonymous datasets that contain the detailed information needed for research purposes. It also may be important to have the possibility to re-identify the research subjects to their personal data. In these cases, data should be pseudonymised to protect the data subject's privacy and minimise the risk to their fundamental rights in the event of unauthorized access. Therefore, all participants should be assigned an identification code so that the different actions of the participants during data collection can be mapped. The relationship between the identification code and the participant is captured in the repository and stored separately and securely. This file is accessible only to the data controller.
- **Feedback:** Participants shall be provided with the possibility to retrieve feedback on the results of research.
- **Privacy:** Researchers must ensure that the way research outcomes are reported does not contravene the right to privacy and data protection.
- **Confidentiality:** It is different from the participant's right to privacy; it refers to how data about the participants will be stored.
- **Data control:** The data subject has the right to access all data processed about him or her, and has the right to demand the rectification, deletion or blocking of data that is incomplete, inaccurate or isn't being processed in compliance with the data protection rules.
- **Informed stakeholders:** Informing stakeholders in detail on ethical aspects of research and evaluation/validation in reporting activities.

The Data Controller takes responsibility for ensuring that training procedures, supervision, and data security arrangements are sufficient to prevent unauthorized breaches of confidentiality.

Each access to the collected data is password protected and is only granted to authorized partners for data processing.

In addition, access to information was restricted to the partners involved in the respective task to ensure their confidentiality. Information technologies were used to securely store, provide, and access data and to manage the rights of users.

8.2.3 Data Protection during Storage and Destruction

- Data from electronic records was stored on secure servers that were backed up weekly.
- In addition, technical measures were in place such as firewalls, regularly updated virus protection and access restriction by password protection.
- Non-electronic files were stored in locked file cabinets in non-public areas.
- Files containing information that could identify a study participant were kept separate from research files in locked cabinets.
- All areas were reviewed regularly to ensure that confidential information is not omitted in open areas.
 - The data subject has the right to ensure that his or her personal data are erased and no longer processed if he or she has withdrawn the consent to the processing.
 - All data from the project pilots and studies considered confidential will be discarded by the end of the project, while only the public models and respective datasets described in detail Annex 1 will be made public.
- Several critical factors relevant to data retention were considered, e.g., the purpose of data retention, the type of open data collected, the policies for access to open data, security measures, confidentiality, and anonymity of data.
- Existing methods and tools for permanent and irreversible data destruction were used, e.g., completely overwriting, and formatting hard disks.
 - Further processing of the personal data collected previously ("secondary use") is not envisaged. In the unlikely event that such a need arises during the project, the consortium will take all necessary steps to ensure explicit confirmation that the beneficiary has a legitimate basis for processing and that appropriate technical and organisational measures have been taken to protect the rights of data subjects. In addition, it will be ensured that the secondary data used in DEQ remain anonymous.

8.2.4 Data Protection Risk Assessment

In the first version of this Data Management Plan (DMP), the possibility of conducting a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) was considered. However, the assessment of data security risks showed that none of the processes studied involved risks related to the processing of personal data—such as accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorized disclosure, or access to personal data that is transmitted, stored, or otherwise processed—which could lead to physical, material, or non-material harm. As a result, it was not necessary to carry out a DPIA.

8.3 Data protection regulation in the non-EU Countries

Although the majority of the DIGIECOQUARRY project was developed within the European area by partners based in countries of the European Union to which the GDPR is directly applicable, two entities not belonging to EU member states participated in the project: The Colombian Association of Petro Aggregates Producers (ASOGRAVAS) and MinTek Industries South Africa (Pty) Ltd.

Regarding the regulatory framework for the protection of personal data in both countries, the main applicable regulations in Colombia and South Africa are:

8.3.1 Colombia and the General Data Protection Law

Since 2012, Colombian legislation has regulated Statutory Law 1581, which functions as a framework for the General Data Protection Law in the country.

This Law recognizes and protects the right that all people must know, update and rectify the information that has been collected about them in databases or files susceptible to treatment by public or private entities. Thanks to this milestone, for example, companies have the obligation to request authorization on the destination and use of the data managed by their users.

In accordance with Colombian legislation, if an improper processing of personal data is identified, Law 1581 suggests resorting to the person directly responsible. However, in situations of total silence, it is possible to appeal to the Superintendency of Industry and Commerce (SIC), an entity that has the obligation to investigate and generate the corresponding fine in case of verifying any procedural anomaly.

8.3.2 South Africa and Protection Personal Information Act (POPI Act)-POPIA

The Personal Data Protection Act 4 of 2013 (POPIA), effective July 1, 2020, is South Africa's first comprehensive law dealing primarily with data protection. Its objective is to make the constitutional right to privacy effective by introducing measures that regulate the collection, treatment and use of personal information by public and private organizations in a fair, transparent, and secure manner.

POPIA's goal is to align South Africa with global data protection legislation and best practices, and in many cases is compliant with Europe's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Since POPIA became law in 2013, there have been various advances, such as the appointment of the Information Regulator in 2016 and the publication of the definitive Regulation in 2018. Without prejudice to the applicable regulations, these countries have not yet been declared by the Commission as countries with an adequate level of protection. That is why it is mandatory to adopt a series of measures in the processing of data within the DEQ project to ensure that the principles and rights described in the previous sections are scrupulously complied with by each of the project partners without diminishing the rights of the subjects.

When personal data is transferred outside the EU, the protection offered by the GDPR will accompany the data. That means that if the data is exported abroad, the controller must ensure that one of the following conditions is met:

- The subject has explicitly given his/her consent.
- The transfer is necessary for the execution of the project.
- The data protection of the non-EU member country is considered adequate.
- Necessary measures are taken to provide the appropriate safeguards, such as the inclusion of specific clauses in the contract concluded with the non-European importer of personal data.

When neither of these exceptions is applicable, the transfer can only be carried out if it is not repetitive, affects only a limited number of interested persons, is necessary for the purposes of compelling legitimate interests pursued by the person responsible for the treatment on which the interests or rights and freedoms of the person concerned do not prevail, and the controller evaluates all the concurrent circumstances in the data transfer and, based on this evaluation, offers appropriate guarantees regarding the protection of personal data.

In this case, the controller will inform the transfer control authority. In addition to the information referred to in articles 13 and 14 of the GDPR, the controller will inform the interested person of the transfer and of the compelling legitimate interests pursued.

In case personal data is transferred from the EU to a non-EU country, the controller must provide details on the type of personal data to be exported. The Controller must confirm that such transfers are in accordance with the Chapter V of the GDPR.

In case personal data are transferred from a non-EU country to the EU, the Controller must provide details on the type of personal data to be imported. The Controller must also confirm that such transfers comply with the laws of the countries in which the data was collected.

8.3.3 IPR

The IPR and knowledge management strategy were defined in D9.1. Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan.

This strategy for the DIGIECOQUARRY was designed according to the background of each partner, the ownership of the foreground identified and the exploitation agreements among the parties. In line with this DMP.

Most of the research data are confidential within the partners at least until the commercialisation starts or until the partners protect the results by new or already identified IPR tools. Some of the data as the raw data are shared by the partners that generates this information due to IP protection [e.g., patent protection, copy protection, etc.]. The information shared, already agreed in CA, is processed data, the outputs of the different expert systems and of the different analytics software and systems.

9 Ethical aspects

An Ethics / Privacy by Design approach is pursued within the framework of the project. This means that ethical and data protection issues were considered and observed during the planning and implementation phase for the entire duration of the project and beyond. This approach is explained in further detail in **D11.1. “Ethics Requirements”**. In any case, the ethical strategy for the DIGIECOQUARRY project will be briefly explained at this point:

- All participants in the project are committed to ensuring their adherence to the ethical principles and to acting in compliance with the laws and codes of conduct.
- Particular attention must be paid to data protection, compliance with the requirements of the GDPR as well as protection of confidentiality and anonymity of participants involved.
- Each partner is responsible for acting in accordance with this rule. To ensure the same ethical and data protection guarantees, all DEQ partners must sign a document of compliance to the provisions contained in the GDPR, including those belonging to non-European states.
- An Informed Consent Form (ICF) will be prepared. The participants care to be informed about, among other things, the objectives of the project, the persons responsible, the methods used, the data collected, the handling and processing of this data, possible benefits, and risks as well as the possibility of withdrawing their participation.
- Partners involved in the project should name an Ethics Responsible Person (ERB). This person is responsible for ensuring that all activities of the respective WP take place in conformity with applicable law, that basic ethical principles are observed and that the anonymity of the participants and the confidentiality of their data are protected.
- An Ethics Advisory Board (EAB), formed by the Ethics Responsible Persons, will support the beneficiaries helping and advising the partners in ensuring compliance with ethical principles, the rights of study participants and conformity with applicable law in the areas of ethics, data protection and related issues.
- Risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons may result from personal data processing which could lead to physical, material, or non-material damage. DEQ Partners will receive an ethical questionnaire to classify the type of personal data that will be processed to evaluate risks based on an objective assessment. The severity and likelihood of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects would be determined by reference to the nature, scope, context, and purposes of the data processing.
- If a high risk is detected, the controller, with the assistance of the DPO, must carry out a DPIA.

10 Data Security

The data produced during the execution of DIGIECOQUARRY project is stored per each pilot site in dedicated servers depending on the use case and expert system for the whole project. According to the previous section, those data are made compliant with the GDPR. This section describes some security principles that are implemented in order to protect against any type of modification. Also, a more thorough management of the servers could be made using the ISO 27001 standards or the BSI-Standards. The security principles are listed below:

- **Authentication:** All the users wanting to get access to the DIGIECOQUARRY data servers have to be authenticated. Also, proper means are used to authenticate the servers. An authentication system will be used to handle the authentication of the users during the course of the project.
- **Authorization:** The access to DIGIECOQUARRY data servers is only available to the authenticated and authorized users. These categories and the rights of those users are defined and enforced. The appropriate access control policies and mechanisms (including physical access control) shall be identified for each trial site and project wide to provide the authorization.
- **Accounting:** In DIGIECOQUARRY any access and modification to a resource by any user is securely logged in order to prevent users from denying that data files were accessed, altered or deleted, when auditing.
- **Confidentiality:** The data stored in DIGIECOQUARRY servers should be encrypted during transmission and storage.
- **Communication Security:** Access to DIGIECOQUARRY servers should be done through encrypted communication channels such as HTTPS and IPsec.
- **Data Integrity:** The data collected during DIGIECOQUARRY should be protected from malicious and accidental modifications by any users during their transmission or their storage. Cryptographic mechanisms such as hash functions and digital signatures shall be used.
- **Availability:** This security principle assures that the DIGIECOQUARRY servers should be available for DIGIECOQUARRY users during the defined interval of service. Also, regular backups of the data should be made.

11 Conclusion

This document constitutes the second and final version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the DIGIECOQUARRY project. It serves as a comprehensive guide for the management of data generated throughout the project, ensuring alignment with key principles of digitalization, data governance, and compliance with European standards and regulations.

The report provides an overview of the key components involved in the digitalization process within DIGIECOQUARRY, offering detailed descriptions of the selected components and their roles in achieving the project's objectives. It also outlines the principles and guidelines necessary to address critical issues such as FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) data principles, Open Access requirements, and GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) compliance. These guidelines establish the foundation for effective data governance and facilitate seamless data sharing within and beyond the project.

Moreover, a comprehensive list of datasets generated during the testing and validation phases at pilot sites is presented in Annex 1. These datasets, created under near-real-world conditions, embody the project's commitment to supporting the digital transformation of quarry processes. The datasets are designed with adaptability and interoperability in mind, featuring generic data models for transport, production, and environmental impact analysis.

By adhering to the FAIR principles, these models ensure that the data produced can be accessed, shared, and reused effectively, contributing to the sustainability and scalability of digitalization efforts in quarrying operations. This DMP reflects the DIGIECOQUARRY project's dedication to fostering innovation, collaboration, and transparency, providing a valuable resource for future initiatives in similar domains.

This final version of the DMP encapsulates the project's strategic approach to data management and its enduring impact on the digitalization of quarry processes, setting a benchmark for efficient and responsible data handling.

References

Document Resource ID	Document Resource name and reference
DR1	EU Grant Agreement n°101003750

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Annexes

Annex 1: List of data to be shared in Zenodo repository

DIGIECOQUARRY Public Deliverables

N.	Deliverable name	WP	Leader	Type	Diss.	Date
D1.1	Requirements for Improved extraction, rock mass characterisation and control report	1	UPM-M	R	PU	M9
D1.2	Requirements for Innovative Treatment processes	1	METSO	R	PU	M9
D1.3	Requirements for Quarry full digitalisation (for Smart Sensors, Automation & Process Control, and for ICT solutions, BIM and AI report	1	AKKA	R	PU	M9
D4.1	Report on IQS ICT requirement analysis	4	AKKA	R	PU	M14
D4.2	Report on IQS design and architecture	4	AKKODIS	R	PU	M30
D4.4	Report on Architecture of the data Warehouse and its integration	4	SIGMA	R	PU	M30
D4.5	BIM- Planning 4D for all the pilots	4	APP	DEM	PU	M30
D4.6	Report on IQS, Services Integration and deployment	4	AKKA	R	PU	M37
D4.7	Report on ICT tools refinements after pilots validation	4	AKKA	R	PU	M46
D5.2	H&S certification roadmap	5	ITK	OTHER	PU	M44
D5.3	Overview of energy consumption of different quarrying process, connections and suggestions for reduction measures	5	MUL	DEM	PU	M36
D5.4	Pre-verified Environmental Product Declaration documentation for pilot plant based on historical data	5	CHALMERS	OTHER	PU	M24
D5.5	Simulation routine implementing environmental related findings	5	CHALMERS	OTHER	PU	M44
D6.1	Pilot (FR) Technical report and achieved results	6	VICAT	R	PU	M30
D6.10	Pilot (DE) Technical report and achieved results	6	CSI	R	PU	M46
D6.11	Pilot (PT) Technical report and achieved results	6	CIMPOR	R	PU	M46
D6.2	Pilot (ES) Technical report and achieved results	6	HANSON	R	PU	M30
D6.3	Pilot (IT) Technical report and achieved results	6	HOLCIM	R	PU	M30
D6.4	Pilot (DE) Technical report and achieved results	6	CSI	R	PU	M30
D6.5	Pilot (PT) Technical report and achieved results	6	CIMPOR	R	PU	M30
D6.7	Pilot (FR) Technical report and achieved results	6	VICAT	R	PU	M46
D6.8	Pilot (ES) Technical report and achieved results	6	HANSON	R	PU	M46
D6.9	Pilot (IT) Technical report and achieved results	6	HOLCIM	R	PU	M46

DIGIECOQUARRY Public and Shared Datasets

This section presents **examples of datasets** generated by expert systems used within the project and transmitted to the IQS platform, contributing to the digitalization of processes. The datasets were collected during the testing and validation phases of the systems deployed at pilot sites. In most cases, the data collected during the testing phases closely resembled real-world conditions, although the systems were still undergoing calibration and fine-tuning. The secondary purpose of this section is to share some of the results obtained, particularly the **data models**. These data models represent significant progress as they are highly generic, modelling specific processes within the quarry (transport, production, environment, etc.) and can be adapted to various types of quarries. These data models demonstrate the systems' ability to adhere to the **FAIR data-sharing** principles. The generalization of data models and formats defined by the project enables the creation of **interoperable** systems. Within the project, the data have been used to create several applications dedicated to monitoring business processes. All generated files are in Zip format. Each Zip file contains an XML description file that details the contents of the archive. Business data are stored within the files included in the Zip. For more details on the contents of the files, please refer to the dedicated deliverable found in the deliverable table. Table 12 identifies the data shared by DIGIECOQUARRY.

Table 13. List of datasets shared by DIGIECOQUARRY

Dataset reference			Dataset Name	KTA	Dataset Description	Reference deliverable	Standards and metadata	File Format	Data Sharing
Pilot Site	Data provider	Expert System							
HOLCIM	Maestro	QProduction	f2d20e058cf7_HOLCIM_IT_Treatment_MAESTRO_SCADA_190225.zip	KTA3.1	An example of plant production data transmitted to the IQS by the SCADA system, including daily-aggregated data from plant sensors	D4.1, D4.2	Maestro, Scada	Zip, Xml and Json	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.
HOLCIM	AKKODIS	IQS – Plant production	24664_HOLCIM_IT_Treatment_AKKODIS_PlantProduction_2025-02-19.zip	KTA4.4 & KTA3.1	An example of plant production data managed by the IQS plant production module to monitor main daily production KPI (Production Index, Production Mass, Total Time, Under Load Time, Capacity, etc.)	D4.2, D4.6	Json	Zip, Xml, Json	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.
HOLCIM	APP	BIM - AutoDesk	1702562527794DB_HOLCIM_IT_BIM.zip	KTA4.1	BIM – IFC file	D4.5	IFC	Zip, Xml and IFC	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.
HOLCIM	Chalmers, Roctim and AKKODIS	PlantSmith	20377_HOLCIM_IT_LCA_PlantSmith_2024-01.zip	KTA6 & KTA4.4	An example of LCA results shared with the IQS by PlantSmith expert system. The results give quantitative estimates for environmental impact based on the results of the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) and Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA). The characterization model in line with EN 15804:2019 has been used. The	D5.4, D4.6	LCA : 15804:2019, json	Zip, Xml and json	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.

					results for the 32 compulsory impact categories for the program operator, EPD International, are given for each pilot site for modules A1-A3 in section 4.2.1, module C in section 4.2.2, and module D in section 4.2.3. The results are displayed for the average of all products produced in 2019 for the declared unit of one ton of aggregate product.					
CSI	DH&P	SMARTQUARRY	20250127_CSI_DE_DHP_ASSET_VALUES.zip	KTA3.3 & KTA3.1	An example of mobile machinery data transmitted to the IQS by the DH&P expert system. The files include raw data aggregated every 3 seconds, along with KPI data (hourly and daily) for various parameters.	D4.6, D6.10	DH&P	Zip, Xml and Json	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.	
CSI	APP	BIM - AutoDesk	1702562214510DB_CSI_DE_BIM.zip	KTA4.1	BIM – IFC file	D4.5	APP	Zip, Xml and IFC	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.	
CSI	Chalmers, Roctim and AKKODIS	PlantSmith	34669_CSI_DE_LCA_PlantSmith_2024-01.zip	KTA6 & KTA4.4	LCA results (same as for HOLCIM)	D5.4, D4.6	LCA : 15804:2019, json	Zip, Xml and json	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.	
VICAT	Maestro	QProduction	b2522871023b_VICAT_FR_Treatment_MAESTRO_SCADA_190225.zip	KTA3.1	An example of plant production data transmitted to the IQS by the SCADA system, including daily-aggregated data from plant sensors.	D4.1, D4.2	Maestro, SCADA	Zip, Xml, Json	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.	
VICAT	AKKODIS	IQS – Plant production	22948_VICAT_FR_Treatment_PlantProduction_AKKODIS_2025-02-19.zip	KTA3.1 & KTA4.4	An example of plant production data managed by the IQS plant production module to monitor main daily production KPI (Production Index, Production Mass, Total Time, Under Load Time, Capacity, etc.)	D4.2, D4.6	Json	Zip, xml, Json	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.	
VICAT	APP	BIM - AutoDesk	1702561459239DB_VICAT_FR_BIM.zip	KTA4.1	BIM – IFC file	D4.5	IFC	Zip, Xml and IFC	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.	

VICAT	Chalmers, Roctim and AKKODIS	PlantSmith, CDMP	21498_VICAT_FR_LCA_PlantSmith_2024-02.zip	KTA6 & KTA4.4	LCA results	D5.4, D4.6	LCA : 15804:2019, json	Zip, Xml and json	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.
VICAT	Metso	Metso Metrics	13494_VICAT_FR_Treatment_MobileCrusher_211124.zip	KTA2.1	Running Hours and Fuel Consumption data of Metso Mobile Crusher	D1.3, D4.2	Metso	Zip, Xml and xlsx	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.
CIMPOR	ARCO	Arco Mineral	20467_AGREPOR-CIMPOR_PT_Treatment_WeighingSystem_ARCO_110325.zip	KTA3.1	An example of weighing system data of 8 conveyor belts transmitted to the IQS by the PLC system.	Dx.y	Arco, SCADA	Zip, Xml and Json	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.
CIMPOR	AKKODIS	IQS – Plant production	20761_AGREPOR-CIMPOR_PT_Treatment_AKKODIS_PlantProduction20250311.zip	KTA3.1 & KTA4.4	An example of plant production data managed by the IQS plant production module to monitor main daily production KPI (tons, t/h, rate production index, etc.)	D4.2, D6.4	json	Zip, Xml and Json	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.
CIMPOR	Abaut	Abaut	13803_AGREPOR-CIMPOR_PT_LS_Transport_Abaut_110325.zip	KTA3.2	An example of mobile machinery data transmitted to the IQS by Abaut expert system. The files include data related to cycles, loading, unloading, duration, distance, etc.	D4.1, D4.2, D6.11	Abaut	Zip, Xml, CSV	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.
CIMPOR	APP	Manual	1702562311492DB_AGREPOR-CIMPOR_PT_BIM.zip	KTA4.1	BIM – IFC file	D4.5	IFC	Zip, Xml and IFC	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.
CIMPOR	Chalmers, Roctim and AKKODIS	PlantSmith, CDMP	11111_AGREPOR-CIMPOR_PT_LCA_PlantSmith_2024_01.zip	KTA6 & KTA4.4	LCA Results	D5.4, D4.6	LCA : 15804:2019, json	Zip, Xml and json	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.
CEMEX	Sandvik	SANDVIK's cloud	23575_CEMEX_ES_Drilling_20240527.zip	KTA1.x	An example of data transmitted to the IQS by the Sandvik platform, including measurements taken during the drilling process. The drilling	D1.1, D4.1	MWD, IREDES	Zip, Xml and Json	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is

		platform			report contains MWD data (DI550 rig data in IREDES format).				deposited in the ZENODO repository.
CEMEX	Abaut	Abaut platform	15797_CEMEX_ES_LS_Transport_Abaut_041224.zip	KTA3.2	An example of mobile machinery data transmitted to the IQS by Abaut expert system. The files include data related to cycles, loading, unloading, duration, distance, etc.	D4.1, D4.2, D6.8	Abaut	Zip, Xml, Csv	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.
CEMEX	APP	BIM - AutoDesk	1695731389825DB_HANSON-CEMEX_ES_BIM.zip	KTA4.1	BIM – IFC file	D4.5	IFC	Zip, Xml and IFC	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.
CEMEX	Chalmers, Roctim and AKKODIS	PlantSmith, CDMP	201902_CEMEX_ES_LCA_PlantSmith_2024-01.zip	KTA6 & KTA4.4	LCA results	D5.4, D6.8, D4.6	LCA : 15804:2019, json	Zip, Xml and json	This dataset is widely open to be used by 3rd party applications and is deposited in the ZENODO repository.

Annex 2: Data management organisation

Figure 11: Data management organisation

Annex 3: Basic record template: Processing record example

Template of a processing record of the controller established in the EU

The following information are the legally required minimum requirements, which shall be made available to the supervisory authority on request (article 30.4 of the GDPR).

Name and address of the Controller				Data Protection Officer			
Name:				Name:			
E-mail:				E-mail:			
Tel.:				Tel:			
Address:							
nº	Purpose	Group Concerned	Category of data	Addressee	Transfer to third party	Erasure time	Measures

Table 14: Template of a processing record of the controller established in the EU

Template of a processing record of the processor established in the EU

The processor is also required to maintain processing records, but the information requirements differ.

Name and address of the processor:		Data Protection Officer:	
Nº			
Controller	Name/address/e-mail/tel.		
Category of processing	Abstract description of the service or services		
Transfer to third countries	If applicable		
Measures according to Art. 32 GDPR	Ex. Measures according to the safety concept+ additional encryption if agreed upon with the controller		

Table 15: Template of a processing record of the processor established in the EU